

Lawyer Recommendation Using Ensemble Method

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Abstract—As the number of legal cases continues to increase exponentially, navigating the intricate landscape of laws and regulations presents a formidable challenge. Identifying the most suitable lawyer for individual legal cases is no easy task. In response, this proposal aims to enhance the efficacy of lawyer recommendation systems by combining the strengths of ensemble framework which includes K-Nearest Neighbors and Decision Tree algorithms. K-Nearest Neighbors excel at capturing local patterns and relationships, while Decision Trees are adept at discerning complex decision boundaries and feature interactions. By stacking these algorithms, a collaborative model that can provide more accurate and reliable lawyer recommendations. The project commences by amassing a comprehensive dataset of lawyers, encompassing their areas of practice, client feedback, and other relevant attributes. The project's objective is to recommend lawyers based on the client's case type, budget, and location.

Keywords—K-Nearest Neighbors, Decision tree, Ensemble stacking

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommendation methods play an essential role in current existence, contribution customers the ability to form cognizant selections from an enormous array of options. The fundamental component of machine intelligence algorithms that transfer custom-made implications to users. There are two basic types of approval schemes: content-placed and collaborative refining.

Collaborative cleaning, in another way, is centred on discriminating a consumer's preferences and intuitions by illustration from a vast dataset of consumer interplays. This approach relies on orders that demand cooperation enclosed by various data beginnings and powers to refine information and patterns. The principal law of collaborative penetrating supposes that if two clients, x and y, share analogous desires in one commodity, it inclined share similar advantages in different products also. Collaborative refining influences past experiences, information, and consumer behaviour to create approvals. It identifies consumers accompanying complementary interests or common inclinations for the lawyer or permissible aid. One of its key benefits is enchantment far-reaching coverage, aim it can create user-appropriate approvals outside needing a deep understanding of the article content.

In the framework it determines correct and useful plans to consumers. To obtain this, the project presents a dual ensemble model that connects [3] and [8] algorithms, professed a hopeful approach to improve advice plan

accuracy across differing rules, containing allowable aids. In the sections that attend, the survey existent introduce the field, present the projected two-fold [6] model, explain the exploratory arrangement and results, and decide accompanying potential future directions for this project.

II. RELATED WORKS

Yadav el. at. [1] an approach called the ensemble recommendation model that combines the K Nearest Neighbour (KNN) and Matrix Factorization (MF) algorithms. The results demonstrate accuracy when compared to using either algorithm thereby improving personalized content recommendations, for users. Though the proposed method is efficient it has integrated the ensemble approach into existing recommendation systems can be non-trivial and may require significant changes to the system architecture.

Dhulavvagol el. at. [2] introduces a hybrid ensemble model that overcomes the limitations of traditional classification techniques. Combining multiple algorithms enhances accuracy and precision for better data-driven decision-making in IT and government sectors. Though the proposed method is efficient it does not explore the performance of the model for multiclass classification, which is common in real-world scenarios.

Nair el. at. [3] addresses the challenge of disease prediction from high-dimensional microarray data. It selects relevant genes and utilizes ensemble-based classification (SVM, KNN, Decision Tree) with the majority voting to enhance predictive performance, mitigating computational risks and improving accuracy. Though the proposed method has effectiveness of these algorithms may vary for different diseases and gene expression profiles.

Amra el. at. [4] explores educational data mining in the context of student performance prediction, utilizing KNN and Naïve Bayes algorithms on secondary school data. The study's goal is to aid the Ministry of Education in early performance prediction for performance improvement, with Naïve Bayes achieving the highest accuracy at 93.6%. Though the proposed method has effectiveness student performance can change over time due to various factors, and the study should consider the temporal stability of the predictive model.

Desrosiers el. at. [5] explores the enduring appeal of neighborhood-based collaborative recommendation methods, known for their simplicity, efficiency, and precision in delivering personalized recommendations. It provides an in-

depth analysis of these techniques, emphasizing their advantages and characteristics. Furthermore, it guides the decision-making process for implementing neighborhood-based recommender systems and offers solutions for addressing challenges like data sparsity and limited coverage in large commercial recommender systems. Though the proposed method is effective but susceptibility to data sparsity, which can lead to limited or inaccurate recommendations, and challenges in handling the "cold start" problem where new users or items lack sufficient data for reliable recommendations.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Loading and Preprocessing:

The code begins by importing necessary libraries, including pandas for data manipulation, and various machine learning modules. And then load the dataset from a CSV file ('new_shuffled_csv_file.csv') into a Data Frame using pd.read_csv. The data set is taken from Datahub. Perform one-hot encoding for categorical features ('Case Type', 'Specialization', 'Location'). Split the dataset into features (X) and the target variable (y), where X contains all features except 'Lawyer ID' and 'Win/Lose', and y is the 'Win/Lose' column.

B. Data Splitting:

Split the data into training and testing sets using train_test_split, with 80% for training and 20% for testing

C. Base Models Initialization:

Initialize two base classifiers: Decision Tree and k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).

D. Stacking Ensemble Creation:

The Create a list of base estimators, consisting of the Decision Tree and KNN. Initialize a Stacking Classifier using StackingClassifier with the base estimators and a final estimator (Decision Tree).

E. Training the Ensemble:

Train the stacking model on the training data (x_train, y_train) using the fit method.

F. Model Evaluation:

Make predictions on the testing data using the stacking model and calculate the accuracy using accuracy_score. Calculate various classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score for model evaluation.

G. User Input for Prediction:

Prompt the user to provide specific data for a new case, including 'Case Type,' 'Price,' and 'Location.'

H. Input Data Preparation:

Create input data for prediction as a Data Frame.
One-hot encode the 'Case Type' and 'Location' based on user input.

I. Making Predictions:

Use the trained ensemble model to predict the outcome for the input data using the predict method.

J. Identifying the Best Lawyer:

Based on the predicted outcome, identify the best lawyer for the specified 'Case Type.' Calculate the win/loss score for each lawyer and select the lawyer with the highest score.

K. Result Display:

Display the predicted outcome, the best lawyer for the given case, their win/loss score, and the accuracy of the model's prediction on the testing data.

IV. PROPOSED MODEL

1. To build a resilient and accurate machine learning model for perfect lawyer recommendation, follow the following steps:

A. Importing Libraries

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import StackingClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
import joblib
```

a) pandas:

As a core component, pandas offer a versatile data manipulation toolkit, enabling data preprocessing and feature engineering in machine learning.

b) train_test_split:

Utilized from scikit-learn, this function divides the dataset into training and testing sets, a pivotal step for assessing the model's generalization performance.

c) DecisionTreeClassifier:

A crucial machine learning tool, DecisionTreeClassifier is employed for decision tree-based classification and regression tasks, serving as the foundation for predictive modeling.

d) KNeighborsClassifier:

This module supports k-Nearest Neighbors classification, allowing the model to make predictions based on the proximity of data points in feature space.

e) StackingClassifier:

By leveraging ensemble learning, the Stacking Classifier merges predictions from diverse classifiers to enhance the overall model's predictive accuracy.

f) accuracy_score:

Essential for evaluating model performance, accuracy_score computes the accuracy of the model's predictions, aiding in the assessment of its effectiveness.

g) joblib:

As an efficient library for lightweight model storage and sharing, joblib simplifies the process of saving and deploying machine learning models. It plays a crucial role in ensuring model persistence and efficient data sharing.

B. Building the model

1) Loading the Dataset:

The code commences by importing data from a CSV file named 'new_shuffled_csv_file.csv' using the Pandas library. This csv file acts as the dataset.

```
# Load the dataset
lawyer_df = pd.read_csv('new_shuffled_csv_file.csv')
```

2) One-Hot Encoding:

One-hot encoding is applied to the 'lawyer_df' dataset, specifically for the categorical features 'Case Type,' 'Specialization,' and 'Location.' One-hot encoding is a data preprocessing technique that converts categorical variables into a binary format, allowing machine learning algorithms to work with these features effectively.

```
# Perform one-hot encoding for categorical features
lawyer_df = pd.get_dummies(lawyer_df, columns=['Case Type', 'Specialization', 'Location'])
```

3) Data Preparation:

The dataset is divided into two essential components for machine learning: the feature matrix (X) and the target variable (y). The feature matrix, denoted as X, contains all the attributes or columns from the 'lawyer_df' dataset except for 'Lawyer ID' and 'Win/Lose,' which are typically used to identify and track lawyers and their case outcomes, respectively. On the other hand, the target variable, y, consists of the 'Win/Lose' column, which serves as the variable aim to predict using machine learning models.

```
# Split the dataset into features (X) and target (y)
X = lawyer_df.drop(['Lawyer ID', 'Win/Lose'], axis=1)
y = lawyer_df['Win/Lose']
```

4) Data Splitting:

The dataset is divided into training and testing sets, allocating 80% for training and 20% for evaluating the model's performance.

```
# Split the data into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

5) Model Initialization and Stacking:

The code initializes two base classifiers, namely the Decision Tree and k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). Subsequently, a list of these base estimators is created, and a Stacking Classifier is initialized using these estimators along with a final estimator, which, in this

case, is another Decision Tree Classifier. This ensemble approach combines the strengths of these classifiers to improve overall model performance.

```
# Initialize base classifiers
decision_tree = DecisionTreeClassifier(random_state=42)
knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=3)
# Create a list of base estimators
estimators = [('decision_tree', decision_tree), ('knn', knn)]
```

Initialize the stacking classifier with a final estimator

```
stacking_model = StackingClassifier(estimators=estimators, final_estimator=DecisionTreeClassifier())
```

6) Model Training and Prediction:

The code trains a stacking ensemble model using the training data and then uses the trained model to make predictions on the testing data. This process helps evaluate the model's performance and accuracy.

```
# Train the stacking model on the training data
stacking_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

Make predictions on the testing data

```
y_pred = stacking_model.predict(X_test)
```

C. User Input:

The code sets specific parameters for the prediction, such as the 'case_type', 'price', and 'location' for the prediction task.

```
# Specify the case type, price, and location for which you want to make prediction
case_type = input("Enter the case type: ")
price = int(input("Enter the price: "))
location = input("Enter the location: ")
```

2.

D. Creating Input Data for Prediction:

The code constructs input data for making predictions by initializing a DataFrame with relevant columns and one-hot encoding the case type and location based on user input.

```
# Create input data for prediction
input_data = pd.DataFrame(columns=X.columns)
input_data.loc[0] = 0
input_data[f'Case Type_{case_type}'] = 1
input_data['Price'] = price
input_data[f'Location_{location}'] = 1 # One-hot encode the location
```

E. Prediction and Finding Best Lawyer:

This section begins with making a prediction for the specified input data using the trained stacking model. Then, it identifies the best lawyer for the given case type based on their historical performance. The code evaluates each lawyer, calculating their win/loss score with respect

to the prediction, and selects the lawyer with the highest score as the best fit for the case type.

```

3. # Make a prediction for
   prediction = stacking_m

# Identify the best lawyer for the case type
lawyer_df_case_type = lawyer_df[lawyer_df['Case Type_{case_type}'] == 1]
lawyer_ids = lawyer_df_case_type['Lawyer ID'].unique()
best_lawyer_id = None
best_score = -1
for lawyer_id in lawyer_ids:
    lawyer_cases = lawyer_df_case_type[lawyer_df_case_type['Lawyer ID'] == lawyer_id]
    total_cases = len(lawyer_cases)
    if total_cases == 0:
        continue

    wins = lawyer_cases['Win/Lose'].sum()
    losses = total_cases - wins
    score = wins if prediction[0] == 1 else losses

if score > best_score:
    best_score = score
    best_lawyer_id = lawyer_id
    
```

F. Accuracy and Results:

This section calculates the accuracy on the testing data and then predicts best lawyer and accuracy of the testing data

```

4. # Calculate accuracy on the te
   accuracy = accuracy_score(y_te

# Display the prediction, the best lawyer, their win/loss score, and accuracy
if best_lawyer_id is not None:
    print(f"The best lawyer for the '{case_type}' case is Lawyer {best_lawyer_id}")
else:
    print(f"No lawyer found for the '{case_type}' case.")

print(f"Accuracy of the prediction on the testing data: {accuracy:.2f}%")
    
```

G. Model Serialization:

Ultimately, the trained ensemble model is serialized and stored in a file named 'trained.pkl' via the 'joblib' library. This saved model allows for future use in making predictions without the need for retraining every time.

```

5. #Save the stacking model as a .pkl
   model_filename = "trained.pkl"
   joblib.dump(stacking_model, model_
   print(f"Stacking model saved to {n
    
```

V. RESULT

Upon fetching inputs from the user, the code will process the input and will return the ID of the lawyer that best suits the particular case type, location, and budget. Here the accuracy of the prediction on the testing data was 85.59%. Additionally the found out even more factors such as F1 score, Precision and Recall and these figures were found out to be 85.75%, 84.67% and 86.86% respectively.

```

Enter the case type: Drug
Enter the price: 890
Enter the location: Vilage Court
The best lawyer for the 'Drug' case is Lawyer 1001
Accuracy: 85.59%
F1 Score: 85.75%
Precision: 84.67%
Recall: 86.86%
Stacking model saved to trainednew.pkl
    
```

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This proposed scheme illustrates the potential of an ensemble-based approach to find the best lawyer based on user input. By harnessing the power of machine learning techniques, this innovative solution effectively addresses the pressing need for a dependable and impartial method of suggesting legal counsel, thereby reducing the reliance on time-consuming and costly attorney searches.

Additionally, this model showcases remarkable proficiency in other essential evaluation metrics. The F1 score, which considers both precision and recall, underlines the system's balance between correctly identifying the best lawyers and minimizing false positives. High precision indicates that the recommended lawyers are relevant to the specific case type, while high recall demonstrates the system's ability to capture the majority of potential candidates. This combination of metrics reaffirms the reliability and effectiveness of the lawyer recommendation system, positioning it as a valuable tool for individuals seeking legal representation.

Continuously refining the ensemble framework by incorporating more advanced algorithms, such as deep learning and natural language processing, to enhance the accuracy and sophistication of lawyer recommendations.

VII. REFERENCES

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